

Assessment of Liberia's Beer Industry Effluent Discharge Parameters in the Context of Urban Sustainability

Kadiatu Amtu Swaray

College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, China

Hui Gong

College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, China

Danyang Zhu

College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, China

Mohamed Yateh

College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, China

Xiaohu Dai

*College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, China;
College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Institute of Carbon Neutrality, State Key Laboratory of Pollution Control and Resources Reuse, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, China*

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Abstract:

Due to untreated brewery effluent and increasing industrial growth, most of Liberia's rivers have considerable water body pollution. The nature and extent of pollution caused by wastewater effluent discharged into these environments have not been thoroughly examined. This study looked into the effects of such effluents on the beer industry in Montserrado, Liberia. It assesses discharged effluent parameters, sustainable management practices, and potential wastewater reuse options within the context of urban sustainability. The findings highlight the need for immediate and substantial intervention to mitigate escalating pollution and associated health

risks. The research also noted for the development of practical national industrial discharge standards, regulatory and management framework, tailored to local contexts, rather than a uniform application of stringent regulations that may hinder sectoral growth and intensify public health issues in under-resourced areas. Furthermore, the effectiveness of some treatment technologies. Technology consideration such as onsite treatment and irrigation that enable water reuse options (cooling, agriculture, and resource recovery) which can significantly reduce the environmental footprint of breweries were recommended. However, the implementation of these technologies may face challenges due to infrastructure deficiencies, financial constraints, and public perception regarding the safety and quality of reused wastewater. The analysis concludes that enhancing wastewater discharge effluents management is key for promoting sustainable industrial growth, improving water conservation, and gaining public trust and acceptance. Achieving these goals requires a concerted effort to strengthen policy, enhance technical capacity, and invest in community engagement to foster a sustainable and economically viable brewery sector.

Keywords: Beer Industry, wastewater reuse, discharge standards, sustainable practices.

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Introduction

Beer is the fifth most consumed beverage globally, making the industry's a significant contributor to the economy (Fillaudeau et al., 2007). The sector holds a strategic economic position with the annual world beer production exceeding 1.34 billion hectoliters in 2002 (Source, 2003). However, the production process has a significant impact on the environment, as it is one of the largest generators of wastewater worldwide. During production, beer alternately goes through chemical and biochemical reactions (mashing, boiling, fermentation and maturation) and three solid–liquid separations (wort separation, wort clarification and rough beer clarification) (Kleyn, Abratt, Chipp, & Goldman, 2012; Van Donkelaar, Mostert, Zisopoulos, Boom, & Van Der Goot, 2016). Consequently, water consumption, wastewater and solid–liquid separation constitutes real economic opportunities for improvements in brewing. Globally wastewater management systems are facing enormous challenges of accelerating water insecurity, and contamination of water resources. According to the UN 80% of sewage is currently discharged without treatment (UNWWAP, 2017). Water consumption and wastewater generation in a brewery is not only an economic parameter but also a tool to determine its process performance in comparison with other breweries (Perry & Villiers, 2003; Unterstein, 2000). The effluents contain organic matter, nutrients, and trace elements etc.

In the contemporary era of industrialization, sustainable water management practices are essential to mitigate environmental impacts and conserve resources for future generations. Advancements in wastewater treatment technologies offer pathways for the sustainable recovery and reuse of industrial wastewater. Processes like anaerobic membrane reactor (AnMBR) technology plays an important role in the treatment of high strength brewery wastewater and have proven effective in achieving a COD removal higher than 98%, with

a biogas yield of $0.53 \pm 0.015 \text{ m}^3 \text{ biogas/kgCOD}$ at $35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. (Shao, Peng, Teng, & Ju, 2008) also treated brewery wastewater in a pilot-scale anaerobic sequencing batch reactor (ASBR) in which a floating cover was employed and results showed that the reactor worked stably and effectively for COD removal and gas production. For the part of wastewaters discharged from boiling and fermentation processes in which high strength organic carbon is contained, anaerobic treatment is believed to be the best choice. High rate anaerobic reactors, such as up-flow anaerobic blanket reactor (UASB) (Parawira, Kudita, Nyandoroh, & Zvauya, 2005), anaerobic granular bed baffled reactor (GRABBR) (Baloch, Akunna, & Collier, 2007) and anaerobic fluidized bed (AFB), have been reported to treat brewery wastewater and a satisfactory COD reduction obtained (Ochieng, Ogada, Sisenda, & Wambua, 2002).

Adopting such measures requires a comprehensive understanding of the characteristics of beer industrial effluent and the implementation of appropriate technologies for its treatment and reuse (Li, Wichmann, & Otterpohl, 2009). In Liberia, this implies a shift towards treatment solutions that not only meet discharge standards but also facilitate water reuse within the industry, supporting a circular economy approach coupled with the establishment of proper water quality guidelines for non-potable reuse is imperative to ensure safety and acceptability for industrial applications that can lead to significant water savings (Arias, Merayo, Millán, & Negro, 2021). The analysis of discharge standards and treatment processes is therefore essential for the beer industry to progress towards sustainable water reuse practices. In this study, the assessment focused on three key points; firstly, the analysis of effluent parameters; secondly, the management of wastewater discharge standards benchmarking Liberia against the World Health Organization (WHO), United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), Nigeria, and Cameroon; and thirdly,

recommending various wastewater reuse options for sustainable water reuse.

Background of Beer Industry in Liberia

Brewery production significantly contributes to Liberia's economy, with two prominent companies; Monrovia brewery incorporated and G5+ incorporated. These, companies have been known for their substantial production rates producing and bottling beverage since its establishment in the 1960s, with beer being the most popular choice. In 2009, beer output totaled 4.2 million liters, down from 4.9 million liters in the previous quarter, representing 58.0% (C. B. o. Liberia, 2009) of the total brewery production during that period. By 2021, beer production was estimated at 17,000 metric tons, placing Liberia at 128th in global rankings. In 2022, Liberia ranked as the 174th largest beer exporter globally, with its main export destinations being the Netherlands and Ireland. In Liberia, beer manufacturing is expected to decrease by 0.2% annually, with an estimated output of 12,260 metric tons by 2026. Since 1966, there has been a 4.4% annual decrease in the beer supply in Liberia. In 2021, the country was ranked at number 136, with neighboring west Africa country Mali producing 12,380 metric tons (Linker, 2022). According to this analysis, the beer industry has the potential to significantly boost economic growth with the right strategies in place. On a global scale in 2019, the beer industry's impact on GDP in lower income countries was around 1.6%, which is nearly twice its impact on GDP in higher income nations, averaging at 0.9% of the national GDP (Economics, 2024)

Problem Statement and Research Significance

The rising demands on freshwater resources coupled with stringent environmental regulations have highlighted the urgent need for the beer industry to tackle the challenges associated with the management of its wastewater. Sustainable brewing practices are important for the beer industry to adapt to the growing pressures of water scarcity, wastewater generation and the increased environmental regulations (Muthukumarappan & Misra, 2013).

In Liberia, the discharge standards for brewery effluent are typically lenient, reflecting the need to protect water bodies from pollution. However, there is an opportunity to transform this challenge into a solution by treating and recycling brewery effluent for secondary uses, such as cooling tower feedwater in industrial facilities and irrigational activities.

The primary problem for the beer industry lies in developing and integrating treatment technologies that can effectively purify wastewater to meet both discharge standards and the quality requirements for reuse in industrial cooling systems and irrigation activities. Achieving sustainable water reuse necessitates a balance between technological efficiency, economic feasibility, and environmental compliance. Therefore, the industry faces the dual challenge of adhering to discharge regulations and advancing toward a more sustainable and circular water economy. The problem statement here centers on identifying and implementing suitable treatment strategies that can convert beer industrial effluent into a safe, sustainable resource for cooling and irrigation purposes, thereby reducing the strain on freshwater resources and promoting environmental sustainability.

This research carries significant implications for resource conservation and sustainable industry practices, potentially setting a precedent for the beverage sector presenting a major opportunity to advance industrialization, wherein wastewater from one process becomes the input for another, thus minimizing the environmental impact. By pinpointing viable treatment options, the study aims to assist breweries in exceeding regulatory compliance and move towards proactive sustainable future. The research also offers the potential to strengthen the resilience of the beer industry against the backdrop of climate variability and water scarcity. The findings from the research will serve as a catalyst for policy developments and corporate strategies that prioritize sustainability, influencing stakeholder engagement and consumer perception in positive ways. Through this study, there is immense potential to expand the scope

of sustainable water management strategies within and beyond the beverage industry.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Liberia is situated at 6°N, 9°W in West Africa and is bordered by the Atlantic Ocean on its southwest coast. It also shares borders with Sierra Leone to the northwest, Guinea to the northeast, and Ivory Coast to the east city of Liberia and located in the northwestern portion of the country. The country has a tropical climate with two seasons: the wet season, which lasts from May to October, and the dry season,

which lasts from November to April. Inland, annual rainfall is 4320mm, and average humidity in the coastal area is 78% during the wet season but drops to 30 percent from December to March when the Sahara's Harmattan winds blow. Water availability per capita is the third highest in Sub-Saharan Africa at 49,028 m³, although dry season flows can be low. Surface water and wetlands account for roughly 14% of Liberia's total surface area. Liberia has a number of significant rivers; the St. Paul River is the second-longest river in the country lying the Mt. Coffee hydroelectric facility and providing the majority of Monrovia's raw water. The study area is located in Montserrado which is county in Liberia with Population of 1.6 million.

Figure 1. Study Area Map

Data Collection and Source

To ensure the accuracy and credibility of the findings, this study utilized a blend of qualitative and quantitative data from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data was collected by means of conducting Survey at the beer production facility to analyze their physicochemical properties, organic materials and heavy metals contaminants (including BOD,

COD, DO, pH, ammonia, nitrate, TDS, oil and grease, phosphate, electrical conductivity, and Pb) present in effluent also assessing treatment technology to determine the efficiency, feasibility, and cost-effectiveness of each treatment method. To analyze current discharge standards, secondary data was collected through a comprehensive review of existing literatures, non-governmental reports, and discharge

standards for beer industry effluents on a national and international level encompassing both governmental regulations from the Environmental Protection Agency of Liberia and industry best practices. These sources provided valuable insights into the management of industrial wastewater. All relevant wastewater

discharge standards in Liberia for industrial wastewater were considered during the assessment. This helped in gaining a better understanding of the context, comparing Liberia's practices to global standards, and pinpointing areas needing more knowledge.

Figure 2. Research Conceptual Framework

Research Conceptual Framework

The study follows a conceptual framework in which the main concepts under consideration are industrial waste effluents, fresh water consumption, and wastewater generation and management options. In terms of the relationship among the concepts, water consumption, and wastewater generation may determine the level of pollutants produced by an industry. Wastewater in its raw form, is typically generated as a continual byproduct of manufacturing processes. The industrial effluent may contain additional liquid waste, including residues from cleaning processes and potential accidental spills resulting in the presence of wastewater from the process. This fluctuation

means that the quality of discharged wastewater may vary depending on these factors, leading to varying levels of pollution. It is of the utmost importance to consider the contextual factors related to waste effluent, such as BOD, COD, DO, etc. In the majority of developing countries, wastewater is typically not treated and is instead released into a river or lake. Farmers then redirect this effluent into their fields to cultivate various crops. Wastewater is being reused in other industries apart from agriculture in several industrialized nations due to various factors. However, this is only done after implementing appropriate treatment methods and following recycling guidelines. Within developing countries, many industries face a shortage of funds, cost-intensive conventional treatment

processes, and an increase in wastewater volumes that exceed the capacity of existing treatment plants. Consequently, a low percentage of wastewater undergoes primary/secondary treatment. These factors play a significant role in determining changes in pollutant load, water reuse patterns, policy implications, and the geographic distribution of wastewater generated.

The reasons for considering these factors are based on how their impacts can influence water consumption, withdrawals, wastewater generation, and environmental pollution in Liberia. In many developing countries, scientific and technical literature is scarce regarding the categorization as well as the supervision of industrial wastewater discharge. This is mostly owing to the wide range of industries and the secrecy surrounding wastewater pollutant generation in the industrial sector. Finally, the insights gained in terms of water consumption, wastewater generation, industrial waste effluents, and discharge standards will be significant in informing policy formation for enhanced management of industrial wastewater. Understanding the design of a measurement approach for industrial effluent quality control is vital. The technical route for the current study is shown in Figure 2, taking into account the above-mentioned factors.

Results and Discussion

Fresh water Consumption in the Beer Industry

Water plays a vital role in the brewery industry, where it is combined with maize, malt, sorghum grits, yeast, and water as the primary raw material (Eumann, 2006). The process commences with malt production, involving the soaking and germination of barley grains (Simate et al., 2011). Throughout the mashing process, water is employed to extract sugars from malted grains, resulting in wort formation. Subsequently, an extensive utilization of water is necessary during the boiling phase wherein hop dissolution and sterilization of wort take place. The next step involves quick cooling through

implementation of a procedure known as wort chilling. Yeast activation during fermentation is contingent upon adequate water supply, which significantly influences the taste and quality of the beer (Kleyn et al., 2012). Usually, the amount of water needed to make beer is much greater than the actual volume of the beer. It takes about 6.0 hectoliters of water to produce one hectoliter of beer on average. A 2003 study revealed that a significant amount of water, ranging from 4 to 11 hectoliters per hectoliter of beer, is consumed during production (Perry & De Villiers, 2003). Another study in 2004 highlighted that producing one liter of beer necessitates 4-10 liters of water (Braeken, Van der Bruggen, & Vandecasteele, 2004). The brewhouse typically consumes 0.013-0.026 m³ of water, the bottling cellar generates 0.006-0.016 m³, and the fermentation cellar generates 0.003-0.008 m³ of water (Werkneh, Beyene, & Osunkunle, 2019). During the study, it was seen that the brewery industry in Liberia consumes 5 liters of water to produce 1 liter of beer. This includes all water used in the process, not just the water that ends up in the beer.

Wastewater Generation in the Beer Industry

Annually, the industry generates over 10 billion tons of wastewater, primarily composed of organic pollutants (Lu, Peng, Zhang, Li, & Li, 2019). It is estimated that approximately ten liters of water are used for every liter of beer produced, with the majority of this water employed in brewing, rinsing, and cooling processes (David Kwame Amenorfenyo & Xianghu Huang, 2019). The byproducts of beer production, such as mash and excess yeast, exacerbate pollution when mixed with wastewater. Additionally, the cleaning of tanks, bottles, machines, and floors results in substantial volumes of contaminated water (Goldammer, 2008). Typically, brewery wastewater contains high concentrations of organic and inorganic compounds and may be disposed of in various ways, including direct discharge into natural water bodies like oceans, rivers, streams, or lakes. Other disposal methods include release into the municipal sewer system, either pretreated or untreated, or treatment at a brewery-owned facility before release. In this

research, it was observed that the brewery industry in Liberia generates about 6.5 liters of wastewater for every liter of beer produced. In Nigeria, brewery effluent has been identified as a significant source of pollution in the Olosun River, characterized by high levels of suspended matter, dissolved substances, turbidity, and COD (Ipeaiyeda & Onianwa, 2009). The average levels of these parameters at the discharge point exceed the specified discharge standards (Senthilraja & Jothimani, 2014). In China, breweries produce approximately 0.3 billion cubic meters of wastewater annually, accounting for 1.5–2.0% of the nation's total wastewater production (Feng, Wang, Logan, & Lee, 2008).

Much like industries in other fields, the brewing industry follows various governmental regulations and environmental laws that govern different aspects of manufacturing, transportation, packaging, marketing, transactions, costing, financing practices, packaging specifications, and alcoholic content standards. Breweries worldwide have adopted the Kyoto Protocol to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and tackle their impact on the environment (Nations, 1998; Protocol, 1997). They also put into practice environmental management frameworks like ISO 14001, Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS), and the International Safety Rating System (ISRS) (IFC, 2007). Schematic diagram of water usage and wastewater treatment process in beer manufacturing industry.

Wastewater Discharge Parameters

Brewery Effluent Parameters

Organic Matter (BOD₅ and COD)

The organic content of wastewater is expressed and measured as BOD. BOD is the amount of dissolved oxygen aerobic biological organisms need to break down organic material in a given water sample. The oxygen content is measured when the test starts and again at the end of five days. The difference in the oxygen content on the first day and the last day is used to calculate the BOD of the wastewater. In breweries, BOD often originates from beer solids, yeast, and residual sugars. Discharging wastewater with a

high BOD into surface waters can rapidly lead to a hypoxic (low in dissolved oxygen) or anoxic (completely lacking dissolved oxygen) state. This can result in elevated death rates among fish and creatures living on the bottom of bodies of water. Anoxic water can also result in the generation of sulfide and methane, giving rise to a range of other hazards. Specific enzymes produced by microorganisms can break down complex organic molecules (like proteins and fat) into simpler forms that bacteria can more easily consume. Due to this, the study assessed the concentration of BOD (over five days) to determine the amount of biodegradable organic matter in water, specifically how much oxygen was required by bacteria and other aerobic microorganisms to break down the organic compounds present in the water over a 5-day period at a temperature of 20°C. In Figure 3a, the concentration was seen at 62.7mg/L in 2018, which exceeded the national discharge limit of 50mg/L, 46mg/L in 2019, 41.2mg/L in 2020, 41.1mg/L in 2021, 39.4mg/L in 2022, and 48.2mg/L in 2023. The study found that the high concentration in 2018 was due to yeast metabolizing sugars to produce alcohol and CO₂ during fermentation. The residual yeast and other fermentation by-products that remain after the beer is processed increase the organic load in the wastewater.

An additional frequently employed parameter in the characterization of effluent is Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD). In effluent samples, it is the most widely used alternative to BOD for rapidly estimating the concentration of organic matter. The COD test can be completed in a matter of hours, which is a significant time advantage over the 5-day BOD test. COD can be utilized by personnel of wastewater treatment systems as a parameter for operational adjustments in near real-time. The COD test ought to be regarded as an autonomous indicator of the organic matter content in a sample of effluent, and not as a replacement for the official BOD test. The research investigated the levels of COD in the beer industry for the period of six years from 2018 to 2023. Figure 3b further illustrates that the concentrations were as follows: 99.7mg/L in 2018, 87 mg/L in 2019,

93.7mg/L in 2020, 95.0mg/L in 2021, 83.3mg/L in 2022, and 90.7mg/L in 2023. It is worth noting that all of these concentrations remained within the permissible discharge standards of 100mg/L in Liberia.

Furthermore, the presence of dissolved oxygen (DO) in beer industrial wastewater can be attributed to several factors and processes throughout the production and wastewater treatment stages. Oxygen is introduced through

aeration, especially If the wastewater is aggressively aerated as part of the treatment process to reduce BOD and promote aerobic digestion, the level of DO could be temporarily elevated. As shown in figure 3c, the concentration of DO in 2018 was 1.78mg/L, 2019 was 2.2mg/L, 2020 was 2.1mg/L, 2021 was 5.4mg/L which slightly exceeded the national discharge standard of 5.0mg/L, 2022 was 2.6mg/L and 2023 was 2.1mg/L.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3. (a) BOD₅; (b) COD; and (c) DO; Concentration for the Period of 6 Years

Solids (TDS)

Additives used during the processing stages, such as Salts and minerals affect the taste and

chemistry of the beer, which then become part of the wastewater. The cleaning and sanitizing chemicals used in the brewing equipment can

dissolve into the wastewater, increasing TDS levels. As a water quality indicator, it is categorized as a measure of dissolved substances that can be either organic or inorganic in nature. In Figure 4, the concentrations were seen at 312.3mg/L in 2018, 317.0mg/L in 2019, 442.9mg/L in 2020, 834.7mg/L in 2021 which exceeded both national and international standard, 417.9mg/L in 2022, and 358.4mg/L in 2023. Many regulatory bodies provide guidelines on the maximum allowable TDS in wastewater discharges to prevent adverse environmental effects. These limits can vary, but common thresholds are often around 500 to 1000 mg/L which is the same maximum limit for the protection of freshwater ecosystems in Liberia. More sensitive environments may have stricter standards.

Figure 4. TDS Concentration for the Period of 6 Years

Trace elements (Pb)

In the treatment system, lead (Pb) can be introduced through the use of equipment and vessels that are made of, or coated with, materials containing lead during the brewing, fermentation, and packaging processes. As this wears down or corrode, Pb particles could be released into the water used during manufacturing processes. However, in the study, Pb maintained the concentrations of 0.01mg/L from 2018 to 2023 which were seen in compliance with the permissible discharge standards (0.01mg/L) of Liberia.

Nutrients (Total Phosphorous, Nitrate, and Ammonia)

Total Phosphorus generation in wastewater from the beer industry can occur due to the use of phosphorus-containing materials, chemicals, and additives, as well as through routine operations and potential incidents within the manufacturing process. As seen in figure 5a, total phosphorus concentration was seen at 0.03mg/L in 2018, 0.01mg/L in 2019, 2.37mg/L in 2020 thereby exceeding the national discharge standards of Liberia, however the concentration dropped to 0 in 2021 and 2022 but there was an increase in concentration again in 2023 (1.67mg/L).

As seen in figure 5b, the concentration of Nitrate in the beer industry was seen at 31.6mg/L in 2018, 35mg/L in 2019, 30.9mg/L in 2020, 30.7mg/L in 2021, 38.5mg/L in 2022, and 33mg/L in 2023. All throughout the years, nitrate was seen in full compliance with the national discharge limits.

Ammonia is more harmful to freshwater aquatic life and can interfere with chlorination processes there the treatment of such wastewater often involves processes that will convert ammonia to less harmful substances before discharge into the environment. In the study, ammonia maintained concentration for the 6 years: 2018 was 0.2mg/L, 2019 was 0.5mg/L, 2020 was 0.2mg/L, 2021 was 0.1mg/L, 2022 was 0.3mg/L, and 2023 was 0.1mg/L. as seen in figure 5c.

Oil and Grease

The wastewater discharge from a beer industry plant also commonly contains oils. When wastewater is discharged into rivers, these oils form a layer on the surface that prevents the oxygen from dissolving and blocks the sunlight from entering and reaching the river beds and river plants. This disrupts the process of photosynthesis and subsequently the river's levels of dissolved oxygen, which in turn kills animals living in the river, such as fish. Over the course of six years, the oil and grease concentrations remained constant at 0.01 and 0.03 mg/L, which is in accordance with the national discharge standards as seen in figure 6.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5. (a) Total Phosphorus (b) Nitrate and (c) Ammonia Concentration for the Period of 6 Years

Figure 6. Oil & Grease Concentration for the Period of 6 Years

pH

The majority of aquatic plants and animals can live in water with a specific pH, which means that slight changes could worsen the quality of life. Slightly acidic water can irritate fish gills, damage membranes, and reduce the number of hatched fish eggs while Water with extremely high or extremely low pH is fatal to aquatic plants and animals. Also, Low pH can kill amphibians because their skin is sensitive to contaminants. In the study values for 2018 were seen at 10.3, exceeding both WHO and Liberia discharge limits, however in 2019, the concentration dropped to 7.2, in 2020 was 6.2, in 2021 was 7.9, 2022 was 8.4 and in 2023 was 8.7. In this study, the concentration exceeded only in 2018 but maintained compliance throughout the rest of the years as seen in figure 7.

Figure 7. pH Concentration for the Period of 6 Years

Salinity/ dissolved inorganics (Electric Conductivity)

As a core physical parameter, the electric conductivity which measures how well a sample of water or similar solution can carry or conduct electrical currents was analyzed (see figure 8). The concentration was 20.1 in 2018, 18.5 in 2019, 16.0 in 2020, 19.3 in 2021, 19.8 in 2022, and 20.7 in 2023. All of these were seen with the national permissible discharge limit of 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

Figure 8. Electric Conductivity Concentration for the Period of 6 Years

International Standards Trend

The establishment of global industrial wastewater management standards can be attributed to the rapid industrialization after World War II. The increase in industrial activity resulted in a significant rise in water pollution, prompting countries like the United States and Western European nations to develop specific measures to address the issue. It was not until the 1970s that the global community started recognizing the worldwide impact of environmental concerns. The 1972 United Nations Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm profoundly impacted the initial worldwide endeavor to create unified environmental policies and set the stage for subsequent initiatives.

In industrialized nations, there is a growing global trend towards implementing strict regulations to control the production and utilization of wastewater treatment effluents. Presently, there is a significant discussion and concern around health and safety concerns that arise from the utilization of wastewater reuse options. Water treatment industries in the majority of nations must provide the parameters of their effluent discharge requirements to an authorized certification authority for evaluation. The parameters undergo a thorough assessment before receiving clearance for usage and being

registered. Most industries in Liberia, as well as numerous highly industrialized countries, are not required to submit their results for approval or registration. As a result, the wastewater sector is exposed to significant hazards, particularly from unethical industries.

Most developed countries opt for WHO standards in dealing with these discharge effluents. Implementing industrial wastewater standards can be a complex process that varies greatly depending on technological, economic, and national factors. For instance, Liberia permits a more extensive range from 5.5 to 9.0, reflecting its environmental and economic constraints. However, the WHO advises a pH range of 6.5 to 8.0 to prevent pipe corrosion and protect aquatic life. Despite the wide range of standards influenced by different environmental, economic, and social factors, the ultimate goal remains the same: achieving environmental sustainability.

Maintaining proper pH levels is of utmost importance, as any imbalance can have severe and immediate effects on aquatic ecosystems and human health. For instance, in 2018, the pH of a brewery was higher than permitted due to its raw ingredients. That led to the immediate use of acid to alter the pH, highlighting the urgency

and potential risks of not adhering to proper pH levels. In terms of other pollutants such as COD, and total phosphorus, Liberia has implemented more stringent regulations compared to the standards set by the WHO, USEPA, Nigeria, and Cameroon. On the contrary, the standard for BOD5 for Liberia is relatively lower in concentration compared to international standards. In 2018, Liberia faced difficulties in meeting its own stringent limits for BOD levels, underscoring the ongoing challenges in ensuring compliance with environmental standards. Similarly, the TDS standards are lower than international standards, yet assessments in 2021 revealed higher concentrations than permitted.

These examples highlight the challenges faced in meeting international wastewater standards in developing countries such as Liberia, where the cost of advanced technological solutions is a major barrier. Environmental concerns are often overshadowed by pressing economic and social demands, making it challenging to uphold strict international standards without strong political backing. However, it is still of utmost importance that wastewater treatments adhere to regulatory standards, as seen in table 1, to safeguard the environment.

Table 1. International Wastewater Discharge Standards

Parameters	Units	Wastewater effluent discharged Standards				
		Liberia (EPA, 2002)	Nigeria (Ipeaiyeda & Onianwa, 2009)	Cameroon (MENP, 2018)	WHO (Organization, 2015)	USEPA (USEPA, 2004)
pH	logH	5.5-9.0	6.5-9.2	6.5-8.5	6.5- 8.0	6.0-9.0
COD	mg/L	100	N/A	250	200	N/A
BOD _{5 days}	mg/L	50	360	30	80	30
DO	mg/L	5.0	N/A	5	N/A	5
TDS	mg/L	500	500-1500	1100	1000	500
Total Phosphorus	mg/L	0.05	N/A	5	0.5	N/A
Lead	mg/L	0.1	0.01	0.1	0.01	0.013
Ammonia	mg/L	2.0	0.5	1.5	0.5	0.02 -2.0
Electric Conductivity	µS/cm	1000	100	1500	1000	N/A
Oil & grease	mg/L	0.5	N/A	10	N/A	N/A
Nitrate	mg/L	40.0	45-50	50	50	N/A

Wastewater Management Situation in Liberia

The Government of Liberia Ministry of Health and Social Welfare and Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has the duty of monitoring the quality of drinking water, wastewater, and supervising the release of industrial waste and managing environmental laws. In 2002, they established a set of National standards that cover a wide range of discharge and water treatment parameters. Enforcement of these standards largely depends on the commitment and resources of national governments. For instance, the Liberia Hydrological Service tasked with managing surface and groundwater quality faced a complete breakdown of its hydro-meteorological network in 1990. It wasn't until 2012, with support from the Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate, that significant rebuilding efforts began in that sector. As a result, effective wastewater management is an urgent issue that has a significant impact on the health and overall quality of life of communities and ecosystem services in Liberia. Liberia is currently facing substantial challenges in the management of wastewater as indicated in most national reports.

The management of industrial wastewater is a significant problem for both national and local industrial firms. Another factor is due to the continuous conflict and political instability in the country, the wastewater management industry has been significantly impacted. Simultaneously, the process of urbanization is also occurring at an exceptional and unparalleled rate. These emerging patterns provide a difficulty for municipalities in Liberia, as they are

responsible for effectively and responsibly handling wastewater. The issues confronting wastewater management in the Liberia industrial sector include and are not limited to inadequate environmental regulations and legislation, limited environmental awareness, inadequate financing and inadequate technology, corruption, and haphazard development.

The issue is further worsened by the ineffective implementation of national wastewater policies and the division of responsibility among key government ministries and agencies in general. The impacts of the insufficient management of wastewater in these industries have a profound and severe effect on several communities. The insufficient management of wastewater generated by most industries has resulted in the pollution of water sources, hence posing a significant threat of water-borne diseases and other health concerns for the population. Other challenges such as a severe deficit in advanced treatment technologies, reliable energy sources, and maintenance capabilities, necessitate significant capital investments for upgrading facilities. Moreover, the inappropriate disposal of wastewater has had adverse consequences on the environment, such as the contamination of rivers and marine ecosystems. The National Water and Wastewater Standards Policy was established in 2002 in response to the growing industrialization in Liberia. This policy mandated that all Liberian counties and municipalities must comply with the standards for water treatment and discharge. Table 2 below presents information on various institutions, their respective mandates, and the functions of their sub-units.

Table 2. Institutional Management

Institution	Mandate	Sub-unit	Subunit function
Environmental Protection Agency	Responsible for coordinating, integrating, and harmonizing the implementation of policies and laws related to the environment, including water.	The Policy council	Formulation of policies and programs for the conservation of natural resources and pollution. According to the Law, the function is to promote sustainability in different areas of the country by prevention and control of pollution.

		Department of Compliance and Enforcement	Provision of technical services to EPA like controlling and monitoring industrial effluent discharge and compliance.
Ministry of Health and Social Welfare		Department of Rural Development	Charged with responsibility for setting water-quality standards and monitoring the quality of water supplied for domestic purposes.
Ministry of Public Works		Department of Rural Development	Providing water supply and sanitation services to rural areas through the provisioning of boreholes, hand-dug wells, and spring boxes. Also responsible for the utilization of sewage or related disposal.
Ministry of Lands Mines and Energy	1. Oversee the development and management of water resources in particular and conduct various investigations required for environmental assessments. 2. Responsible for granting water permits to water users and provides	Department of Mineral and Environmental Research	1. Technical support to other government agencies for all aspects of water. 2. Resources development, including water quality issues.
		Liberian Hydrological Service (LHS)	3. Technical wing of the ministry with specialists in engineering/environmental engineering.
		The National Water Resources and Sanitation Board	4. It acts as an advisory body at central level water supply and sanitation projects.
Liberia Water and sewer cooperation	Mandated to provide drinking water for inhabitants in both urban and rural areas.	Technical department	1. Operates as a commercial entity and is responsible for water and sanitation. 2. maintaining water and sewer facilities, offices, and/or agencies within and everywhere in Liberia.

Wastewater Reuse Options

Navigating towards a sustainable future, the paradigm in wastewater management is evolving from mere treatment to embracing reuse and recovery systems. The sanitation sector, poised at the forefront of this transformative shift, offers immense potential for contributing to sustainable practices. Therefore, there is a compelling need for more demanding standards specifically designed for the reuse of treated industrial effluent, alongside strong policies to enforce resource conservation and sustainable industry protocols. Berndtsson, J.C. and K.

Jinno (Berndtsson & Jinno, 2008) success in using reclaimed water and rainwater in buildings is a noteworthy example of industrial synergy. By using technically advanced solutions for water reuse, the city was able to reduce its dependency on freshwater resources and demonstrated how merging the water and wastewater sectors can lead to the optimization and sustainability of urban water systems. Based on the current analysis of the discharged effluents parameters assessed, the brewery industry can opt for the following wastewater reuse options as outlined below:

Application in Cooling system

The treated water can be used to replace or supplement the make-up water in cooling towers. In a cooling tower, water is used to absorb heat through evaporation, thereby cooling the remaining water, which can be recirculated. Because part of the water evaporates, make-up water is continuously needed to replace the lost volume and maintain system balance. As the treated water passes through the cooling tower system, it absorbs heat from the processes or equipment being cooled, which is then dissipated into the atmosphere through evaporation and drift. For instance, in some European countries, industrial facilities have started using treated effluent as cooling water. By doing so, these facilities have greatly reduced their withdrawal of fresh water, minimized thermal pollution by reusing the effluent, and often improved their overall water efficiency.

Application in Irrigation

The brewery's treated effluent, rich in organic materials and nutrients, can be beneficial for agricultural irrigation. This recycles nutrients and can reduce the need for chemical fertilizers, which are energy-intensive to produce and can cause environmental damage if not managed properly. By reusing treated effluent for irrigation, the brewery can contribute to creating a closed-loop system where water and nutrient cycles are connected, leading to reduced effluent discharge into the environment. This practice can also foster collaboration with local agriculture, creating a symbiotic relationship where breweries supply nutrient-rich water for crops possibly used in their brewing processes, such as barley or hops, enhancing the idea of industrial synergy. Reclaimed water usage cuts down on greenhouse gas emissions associated with water extraction, treatment, and distribution, as well as with wastewater treatment. Implementing such sustainable practices can help breweries achieve certification for environmental management systems, like ISO 14001, improving market reputation and potentially increasing customer base due to the growing number of environmentally conscious

consumers. For example, in various Mediterranean countries such as Spain, Italy, Cyprus, and Greece, treated wastewater is increasingly used for crop irrigation. For instance, in Gran Canaria, 20% of water used across all sectors comes from treated wastewater, which is also used to irrigate thousands of hectares of tomato and banana plantations. This practice allows for more efficient use of freshwater by avoiding discharge to the sea and contributes to the substantial fulfillment of agricultural water demand (Voulvoulis, 2018).

Resource Recovery

Wastewater treatment processes can also enable the recovery of valuable by-products such as nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus) or biogas (methane). These by-products can be reused within the brewery or sold for additional revenue.

Direct Reuse

The installation of advanced treatment systems in the study plant location can purify wastewater from breweries to a level that is appropriate for direct reuse in the brewing process. This approach has the potential to aid brewing companies in lowering their freshwater use as well as their output of effluent. In addition, on-site treatment methods such as physical, chemical, and biological processes can be used to remove contaminants and pathogens; the treated wastewater can then be reused for non-potable applications such as cleaning.

Existing treatment technology

After production of beer wastewater is collected and transported by a network of pipes and pump stations to a treatment plant which can be treated in a series of steps (as shown in Figure 9). The conventional sequence goes from pre-treatment to primary and secondary, and sometimes tertiary, treatment. The treated effluent is eventually discharged, usually to a nearby water resource.

When the sewage arrives at the WWTP, it is collected in an equalization tank. The purpose of this tank is to stabilize flow because an even flow rate is essential for plant operations. Changes in

the volumes entering the tank, measured by flow meters, alert operators to possible problems upstream and the need for operational adjustments. Pumping stations transfer raw sewage from the equalization tank into the facility for initial treatment. This early phase, known as preliminary treatment, employs screens to capture large solids in the inflowing wastewater. As the wastewater enters the facility, it passes through a bar screen that filters out substantial debris like bricks and broken glass, which can obstruct or damage treatment equipment if not removed. The primary treatment phase focuses on extracting suspended solids, primarily organic, along with fats, oils, and grease. In large-scale treatment

plants, this process involves primary clarifiers where oils and fats rise to the top and heavy solids settle at the bottom. Skimmers remove grease and other floating debris, preventing them from clogging pumps. The wastewater moves slowly in the primary clarifiers, and occasionally, chemicals like aluminum are added to hasten sedimentation. This sediment, called primary sludge, is later dewatered and disposed of in landfills. Primary treatment typically reduces biological oxygen demand (BOD) by 20-30%, removing about half of the suspended solids and nitrogen, but leaves most phosphates.

Figure 9. Existing Treatment Technology

Secondary treatment aims to further eliminate organic matter and ammonia, essential for safeguarding drinking water and aquatic habitats. Various technologies are used, including activated sludge processes, bio-filters, and pond or constructed wetland systems. However, the aeration tank, where biological processes decompose organic matter and ammonia by blending microorganisms with the wastewater, is prevalent in Liberia. These microorganisms convert organic matter into carbon dioxide,

water, and energy, crucial for their growth and reproduction, and break down ammonia into nitrates and nitrogen. The activated sludge process involves pumping effluent from the primary clarifiers into an aeration basin with distinct anoxic and oxic zones. The anoxic zone supports microorganisms that thrive with less oxygen, while the oxic zone uses diffusers to saturate the microorganisms with oxygen. The wastewater remains in the aeration basin for

about 10-20 days, known as the solids retention time (SRT).

Tertiary treatment, or advanced treatment, goes beyond previous steps to eliminate additional contaminants or specific pollutants, often through chemical disinfection, which is commonly used in Liberia. This stage can remove nearly all impurities from sewage, though it is typically costly. Despite reductions in microbial counts through each treatment stage, significant numbers of pathogenic organisms can persist. Thus, disinfection aims to eliminate or deactivate these pathogens. Following the final treatment, the purified effluent is released, generally into bodies of water like streams or rivers, depending on its intended use, whether agricultural or industrial.

Recommended Technologies for Wastewater Reuse

As water scarcity becomes an ever-increasing concern in today's global economy, sectors are pressured to reconsider their water management strategies. Breweries, notable for their substantial wastewater production and water usage, are investigating novel approaches to repurpose wastewater for irrigation and refrigeration systems. This practice not only mitigates water scarcity but also promotes social responsibility and environmental sustainability. The brewery industry, similar to numerous other sectors, encounters difficulties in efficiently managing its effluent. Additionally, due to the depletion of water resources, the release of untreated effluent pollutes the environment. In response to increasing public consciousness and stringent regulations, breweries are presently exploring sustainable alternatives to tackle these obstacles.

Reverse Osmosis treatment technology for wastewater Reuse in cooling system

Reverse osmosis is an increasingly adopted technique within the brewery industry for the purpose of effluent treatment. This procedure renders effluent suitable for reutilization in cooling systems by reducing contaminants and impurities. Although reverse osmosis systems may require a substantial initial investment, the

long-term economic advantages significantly surpass the expenses. Reusing treated effluent can help breweries reduce operational expenses and water usage. Furthermore, treated effluent has environmental benefits when utilized in cooling systems. It mitigates the burden on freshwater resources and restricts the release of contaminants into the surrounding ecosystem. Reverse osmosis technology implementation enables breweries to exhibit their dedication to environmental stewardship and sustainability.

Denitrification treatment technology for wastewater Reuse in Irrigation

Breweries can reuse wastewater not only for cooling systems but also for irrigation by utilizing denitrification technology, which effectively removes nitrogen compounds from wastewater, making it suitable for agricultural use. Despite some concerns about the social acceptability of using treated wastewater in agriculture, evidence from various studies assures that the proper treatment processes maintain the safety and quality of the irrigation water. This technology stands out as a relatively economical and efficient method compared to other wastewater treatment technologies, offering brewery industries a sustainable option for wastewater reuse. By adopting denitrification for wastewater management strategies in Liberia, brewery industries can improve environmental impact. While there might be apprehensions about the social acceptance of using treated wastewater for farming, research confirms water safety and quality, supporting its use in agriculture. In contrast to other wastewater treatment options, denitrification provides a practical and cost-effective solution for breweries interested in sustainable wastewater reuse. By integrating denitrification into wastewater management practices, brewery industries support global water conservation initiatives similar to those in regions like China, Nigeria, and Cameroon.

Industrial Wastewater Discharge Standards to consider for reuse option

While one fixed set of standards can simplify implementation and monitoring, it can also neglect the benefits and risks of wastewater. For

example, in an irrigation context, wastewater composition, soil characteristics, type of crop, and protection measures can influence risk. Certain trace elements can affect the integrity of soil structure and accumulate in crops, rendering them unfit for human consumption. Considering the quantities of wastewater generated in Liberia and the growth in agriculture produce, the treatment of wastewater using technology like denitification to remove of high nutrient is essential however there should be require standards to aid the process. Even though reuse options are step to greener future, without proposing nuanced and feasible pollution control measures, can lead to failure of regulations address the reality on ground and existing risks to a large proportion of the population, particularly farm laborer and the poor.

The core focus of establishing reuse standards primarily centers on guaranteeing safety, promoting sustainability, and ensuring economic viability. These standards aim to optimize resource utilization, minimize harm to the environment, and safeguard public health. Standards are very important in areas like reusing water because they help figure out the right amount of treatment for different uses, such as industrial processes and irrigation in agriculture. Similarly, in the field of materials and product reuse, standards are vital in ensuring the quality and safety required for effectively repurposing goods. These criteria are typically based on scientific research, risk assessments, and technological capabilities, in line with regulatory requirements and industry standards. Ultimately, the implementation of reuse standards is vital in fostering a circular economy that takes into account ecological, economic, and social considerations.

Liberia

In Liberia, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) plays a significant role as the governing regulatory authority, overseeing various regulations to ensure environmental sustainability. Key regulations include the Water Quality Regulation of Liberia (Environment Protection Agency Republic Of Liberia, 2018; R.

o. Liberia, 1978), Wetlands regulation of Liberia (Environmental Protection Agency Republic of Liberia, 2019), Environmental Protection and Management Law of Liberia (EPA, 2002; M. L. M. a. E. M. Liberia, 2020) Environmental and Social Impact Assessment Guideline (Agency, 2006), Chemical Guideline of Liberia (Agency, 2020), WASH Commission Act (R. O. Liberia, 2012), and the Integrated Water Resource Management Policy (Ministry of Lands, 2007). The Water Quality Regulation focuses on safeguarding drinking water sources, preventing contamination, and establishing quality requirements for surface and groundwater, rivers, lakes, and coastal areas. Concurrently, the Wetlands Regulation addresses wetland conservation, with Liberia as a signatory to international agreements like the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands. Protective measures, such as the National Wetland Policy, aim to promote biodiversity preservation and integrate wetlands into national development planning.

The Environmental Protection and Management Law, enacted in 2002, serves as a comprehensive legal framework addressing various environmental concerns, including air and water quality, biodiversity, and environmental impact assessment. This law establishes a solid foundation for managing environmental challenges in Liberia. The ESIA Guideline directs the assessment of social impacts arising from development projects, outlining the institutional structure of ESIA in Liberia. It emphasizes capacity-building initiatives for stakeholders involved in the ESIA process, ensuring a holistic approach to evaluating the social implications of development. The Chemical Guideline manages the storage, transportation, and disposal of chemicals within the country. It includes crucial components such as registration and notification requirements for manufacturers and importers, along with labeling and packaging standards to minimize risks associated with chemical handling.

The WASH Commission Act, signed into law in 2017, establishes a commission responsible for monitoring and coordinating activities in the water, sanitation, and hygiene sector. The

commission strives to ensure that every citizen in Liberia has access to safe drinking water, better sanitation facilities, and proper hygiene practices. The Integrated Water Resource Management Policy focuses on sustainable water resource management, addressing challenges such as limited access to potable water and climate change effects. Policy stresses cross-sector collaboration for strong coordination.

New Zealand

New Zealand's regulations on drinking water quality are summarized in the Drinking Water Standards, which define the criteria for five specific water treatment chemicals: hydrated lime, aluminium sulfate, fluoride, EPI-DMA polymers, and chlorine. These standards mirror those of the European Standards Institution and the American Water Works Association, providing a framework for manufacturers, vendors, and distributors to ensure that these chemicals adhere to the requisite physical and chemical quality standards. Oversight of the safe provision of drinking water is a duty assigned to regional councils, guided by policies from the Ministry of Health [New Zealand Ministry of Health, 2007].

China

To ensure the safety and regulate the utilization of reclaimed water, the government has set forth specific quality requirements. Under the government decree titled Urban Wastewater Reuse Category (GB/T 189198-2002), the scope of wastewater reuse is categorized into five distinct segments, each associated with its own set of recommended national standards. These include the Urban Wastewater Reuse Water Quality Standard for Urban Miscellaneous Water (GB/T 18920-2002), which outlines the quality, sampling, and analysis methods for urban miscellaneous water (Ministry of Ecology and Environment, 2004, 2005; Xu et al.). The standard for Scenic Environment Water (GB/T 18921-2002) details the quality and usage patterns for reclaimed water in landscape environments. For industrial applications, the Urban Wastewater Reuse Water Quality Standard for Industrial Water (GB/T 19923-2005) sets the parameters. Groundwater

recharge is governed by the Urban Wastewater Reuse Water Quality Standard (GB/T 19772-2005), which includes control measures and monitoring requirements. Lastly, the standard for Farmland Irrigation Water (GB 20922-2007) defines the quality control, requirements, and analysis methods needed for agricultural use.

To support the implementation of these categories, the Ministry of Construction and National Standardization Administration have developed additional guidelines and construction standards aimed at promoting efficient wastewater reuse. These include the Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plant Construction Quality Acceptance (GB 50334-2002), the Code for Design of Wastewater Reclamation and Reuse (GB 50335-2002), and the Architecture Design for Reclaimed Water System (GB 50336-2002). Each standard plays a key role in framing the infrastructure and design principles necessary for effective wastewater management and reuse

United States

In the United States, the Federal Safe Drinking Water Act (SDWA) delegates the oversight of drinking water quality to individual states, without establishing a unified federal framework for Drinking Water Treatment Chemicals (DWTCs). State-level Safe Drinking Water Regulations (SDWR) frequently incorporate specific clauses for DWTCs. According to Drew and Frangor (2002), while the majority of states adhere to nationally recognized standards, these are predominantly issued by the NSF or the American Water Works Association (AWWA). There are generally two types of standards relevant to DWTCs: the Health Standards (NSF/ANSI 60 and 61), which are designed to mitigate health risks associated with process chemicals, and the technical and performance standards, typically governed by the AWWA Standards (ANSI/AWWA Standards) along with other standards from the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) and the American National Standards Institute (ANSI), the latter serving as the accrediting body in the U.S.

South Africa

In South Africa, the criteria for wastewater quality are specified across various national regulations and guidelines. The Department of Water and Sanitation plays a crucial role in defining these standards, prominently through the South African Water Quality Guidelines for Domestic Use. To ensure facilities meet these standards, the Green Drop Certification program conducts regular inspections and regulates wastewater treatment and management facilities. These comprehensive standards cover a wide array of attributes to maintain and enhance water quality, ensuring it is safe for home use and environmentally sustainable. To address the risks associated with poorly treated wastewater, a detailed eight-volume set of guidelines has been established. These volumes cover a broad scope: Volume 1 for domestic use, Volume 2 for recreational use, Volume 3 for industrial settings, Volume 4 for agricultural use related to irrigation, Volume 5 for livestock watering, Volume 6 dedicated to aquaculture, Volume 7 focused on aquatic ecosystems, and Volume 8, which serves as a field guide.

Economic and Risk Implications

There is the potential for major economic and risk implications associated with the reuse of wastewater in the beer industry. In terms of economic impact, it has the potential to cut down on water use as well as the costs associated with water treatment and disposal. In addition to this, it offers the possibility of generating revenue through the sale of treated wastewater or by-products that are produced as a result of wastewater treatment processes. On the other hand, there are potential risks that need to be properly addressed, such as compliance with regulations, investments in infrastructure, and the perception of the public. In addition, incorrect treatment of wastewater can result in environmental contamination and cause harm to public health, which poses dangers to brewers in terms of both their legal standing and their reputation. Therefore, it is vital to adopt appropriate treatment technologies and comprehensive monitoring systems to avoid

these risks and ensure that the brewing industry sustainably reuses wastewater.

Conclusion

Liberian authorities are confronted with the daunting challenge of protecting the environment, promoting economic growth, and ensuring public health due to the increasing population and inadequate wastewater treatment facilities. In this study, an analysis of discharged effluent parameters, sustainable management practices, and wastewater reuse options of a brewery industry in Monsterrado, Liberia is presented. The rapid increase in pollution levels within the industrial sector necessitates swift intervention. However, implementing a single set of strict national standards without a well-defined development plan carries the risk of impeding overall sectoral growth due to the substantial investments required. This, in turn, could lead to higher pollution levels and public health concerns in underserved regions. Implementing a single set of national standards for discharging industrial wastewater is unlikely to effectively limit potential risks of pollution and water insecurity in most counties in Liberia. To effectively address Liberia's industrial challenges, it is necessary to first strive for a comprehensive set of diverse industrial standards across the entire country as evidenced by other regions in the world. This should be accompanied by the establishment of a strong management and compliance basis, which would enable the implementation of more refined guidelines in the future. In pursuit of this objective, the discharge standards established in 2002 may not provide a more practical and attainable foundation for national-level discharge regulations compared to the currently proposed standards. By evaluating various treatment technologies that facilitate water reuse and highlighting significant research into the characterization of brewery effluent data analyzed, the research also provides insight into wastewater reuse options associated with brewery wastewater. Brewery wastewater may be reused using a variety of treatment and recycling methods onsite treatment, irrigation, resource

recovery, cooling systems, etc. However, it also requires careful management to mitigate risks such as health and environmental degradation, regulatory compliance, infrastructure investment, public perception, and operational challenges. Furthermore, the results indicate that the existing effluent management practices in Liberia are notably less sophisticated, as a result, the brewery industries continue to face obstacles. This underscores a policy and infrastructure deficiency in Liberia that requires attention to enhance sustainability practices. Adopting sustainable reused water technologies not only ensures adherence to more stringent environmental regulations but also improves the overall operational effectiveness of breweries, yielding a financial gain within between three and five years. Maintaining and operating these systems can be complex and require skilled personnel, leading to operational challenges and cost implications. Also, most nearby communities are engaged in subsistence farming, the public may have concerns about the safety and quality of the reused wastewater, leading to public resistance to these wastewater reuse projects. In summary, the primary benefit derived from implementing effective effluent treatment has the potential to reduce its ecological impact substantially and preserve water resources.

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